

THE USE OF ENGLISH SIMPLE SENTENCES BASED ON MODERN LINGUISTIC METHODS

Zamira Shukurova

Faculty of Foreign languages Karshi state university

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Abstract. *Language is the most important tool of human communication, formed in the process of social development and serves the common good. Since the emergence and development of language is related to the development of society, the source of study of all sciences that think about human perfection is related to language.*

Key words: *syntactic analysis, connections, comprehensive analysis, components.*

УПОТРЕБЛЕНИЕ ПРОСТЫХ ПРЕДЛОЖЕНИЙ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА НА ОСНОВЕ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИХ МЕТОДОВ

Аннотация. *Язык – важнейший инструмент человеческого общения, сформировавшийся в процессе общественного развития и служащий общему благу. Поскольку возникновение и развитие языка связано с развитием общества, то и источник изучения всех наук, размышляющих о совершенствовании человека, связан с языком.*

Ключевые слова: *синтаксический анализ, связи, комплексный анализ, компоненты.*

The role of any state in the world community is largely determined by its scientific potential, the development of science. For the development and progress of our country, of course, knowledge of languages is important for the training of leading specialists in the field. In particular, in the field of linguistics, the study of syntax in world languages, in particular English, is a modern requirement.

Language, as a social phenomenon, forms the communication between individuals and societies, and the basis of this communication is speech construction. There are a number of linguistic methods in the study and analysis of speech structure that have been used for centuries. Studying the syntactic level of a language requires new approaches. However, traditional syntactic analysis methods cannot reveal syntactic connections and the semantics of syntactic units, consequently the need for syntactic-semantic analysis of the sentence structures of language units indicates the relevance and necessity of the chosen topic.

In world linguistics, along with the phonological, lexical and semantic layers of language, scientific research is being conducted to determine the semantics of functional analysis and

syntactic units. At the syntactic level, which is important in linguistics, there are different approaches to the theory of analysis. From this point of view, one of the pending problems in linguistics is that research should be conducted on complaints to determine the semantics of parts of speech in the paradigmatic and syntagmatic directions of speech units, and to reveal the semantics of syntactic units.

In world linguistics, the theory of syntactic semantic analysis has been a constant focus of linguists. A number of scientific and theoretical studies in general linguistics have been carried out in this regard (S.D.Katsnelson, V.V.Burlakova, N.N.Stepanova, S.M.Kibardina, A.M.Peshkovskiy, N.I.Filicheva, V.A.Frolova, A.S.Filatova, I.B.Dolinina, M.D.Stepanova, E.V.Razova, U.I.Yuldasheva, M.V.Vlavatskaya, J.Erben, G.Xelbig, Yu.D.Apresyan, B.A.Abramov, N.P.Bilimovich, G.Zandau, K.E.Zommerfeldt, V.Bondsio, V.V.Korablin, E.A.Krasilnikova, R.Longakr, E.P.Logaceva, S.Schuller, V.Kolarova, E.Sausa, A.Malchukov, B.Comrie, J.Panevova).

At the same time, scientific observations have been made on this issue at all levels of language. Uzbek linguists also rely on lexical meaning to define valence at the syntactic level. Including J.Buronov, N.Q.Turniyozov, I.K.Qochqortoev, R.Rasulov, M.M.Mirtojiev, A.Nurmonov, S.H.Muhamedova, Z.Mirzakarimova, A.Choriev, U.I.Yuldasheva, D.T.Hojieva, V.A.Karimjonova, Sh.A.Ganieva studied valence determination at the lexical and syntactic level.

In the study of the problem to be solved in the given literature, we have seen that the work is based mainly on the function of syntactic units in speech and their lexical-semantic aspects.

This study focuses on identifying the differential syntactic, syntactic-semantic features of syntactic units in English sentence structures and their ability to combine with other syntaxes based on specific syntactic connections. Since the analysis of traditional parts of sentences in syntactic analysis is not fully justified, in this study, new methods of syntactic analysis, i.e. the method of analysis of transformational method, immediate constituents (IC), defining components and syntaxes, were used. In component analysis, syntactic units form the surface structure of sentences. In synthetic analysis, syntactic units, on the other hand, cover the deep structure of sentences.

A comprehensive analysis of language, which is the field of study of linguistics, requires methods appropriate to the development of science. Any method that analyzes each area must meet the following requirements.

1. The method must be objective. The result should be the same regardless of the time and place of application of the method. Subjective approaches have a negative impact on the value of the method.

2. The method should be consistent and based on clear concepts.

3. The method should be universal; i. e. be able to analyze the main sections of the field (at least four).

4. The method should be as simple as possible.

There are several methods used in linguistics. There are two types of these methods:

1. General methods.

2. Methods of linguistic analysis.

These methods work in conjunction with each other and draw specific conclusions.

General methods are methods that apply to all aspects of the social sphere. In particular, the methods of analysis from general to specific, from private to general, analysis-synthesis, from simple to complex are used in almost all areas.

The methods of linguistic analysis are unique to linguistics and serve to provide scientific conclusions about the science.

In modern linguistics, the following methods are used for linguistic analysis;

- part of speech method; • historical-comparative method;
- substitution (substitution) method; • distributive method;
- method of disassembly; • transformation method;
- statistical analysis method; • method of meaning scale analysis.

The method of fragmentary speech has been used since the early days of linguistics. According to this method, sentences are divided into parts. It is based on the function of the word in the sentence.

The analysis of the sentences is as follows:

1. The sentences are divided into main parts of speech (subject and predicate) and secondary parts (complement, determiner, adjunct).

2. The function of the parts of speech is to determine which phrase is being used.3. The grammatical forms (morphological categories) of the words that come as a part of speech are explained [Babayeva, 1981]. This method only works in the syntax section. The complexity of using this method is observed in almost all languages.

The historical-comparative method is the primary method on which comparative-historical linguistics is based. This method is based on the comparison of the diversity of languages of the world, the similarities and differences between them. This method solves the following problems:

1. To determine whether languages are related or not related by comparing their characteristics and similarities with other languages.

2. A comparative study of cognate languages to determine the common genetic basis for them; the use of retrospective comparison in the study of this analysis. This is done by comparing the current state of languages to their historical aspects.

3. The gradual development of languages is studied, that is, a comparative analysis of the path of development of the language to its current state. Such a comparison is called a prospective comparison. In this case, historical written monuments serve as a primary source [Barkhudarov, 1975].

Using this method, a family of languages is determined. For example, the Indo-European language family, the Turkic language family, the Mongolian language family, and so on. Language families are further subdivided according to certain characteristics. In particular, Turkic languages are divided into about thirty groups. The substitution method is based on the substitution of parts of sentences. The methodological changes that take place in speech are analyzed by replacing them with language units and other alternatives that are in a certain place. This method determines the place of synonyms, antonyms and homonyms in the lexical system. The distributive method analyzes the ability of language units to interact with other units in the speech process. Distribution can be interpreted as a "syntactic possibility". For example, the ability of a word, morpheme, or phoneme to interact with another word, morpheme, or phoneme, is called the distribution of these units.

There are morphological, syntactic and lexical-semantic types of distribution. Morphological distribution is the ability of a word in one category to interact with a word in another category: adjective with noun, form with verb.

The method of subdivision analyzes any whole, in particular a sentence, as consisting of parts that are in a relationship of dominance and subordination. This method works at the grammatical level: morphology and syntax [Boronov, 1973].

The transformation method is the most perfect of the modern methods. This method is characterized by the ability to explain the syntactic process in language.

Statistical analysis is used at all levels of language and is therefore universal. This method accurately shows the level of use of language units and language events in speech. The method of semantic analysis analyzes the lexical meaning of a word by dividing it into separate semantic aspects. This method is important for clarifying the meaning of polysemous words.

In general, the role of linguistic methods in determining the most general and specific laws specific to the field of linguistics is invaluable. We syntactically analyze sentences, first of all, we need to have a thorough knowledge of syntactic relations, although if we do not know syntactic relations, we can't get the right direction in the analysis of sentences not only on the basis of traditional but also modern methods of analysis. To this end, we have devoted the next section to the syntactic connections used in the analysis methods we intend to use in the second chapter.

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